

REPRESENTATION OF THE WILL GENRE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *In this article, the field of the concept that has been of interest to linguists has been looked at, and the revelation of the concept of death in wills and uiae as examples of genres has been explained. Explained based on examples and tables.*

Key words: *linguistics, genres, concept of death, speech genres, wills with legal and physical force.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассмотрено интересующее лингвистов поле концепта, объяснено раскрытие концепта смерти в завещаниях и улаэ как примерах жанров. Объяснение на примерах и таблицах.*

Ключевые слова: *языкознание, жанры, понятие смерти, речевые жанры, завещания с юридической и физической силой.*

In linguistics, the determination of the linguistic characteristics of the will is also carried out by determining its genre characteristics. It is known that the concept of linguistic genre means any speech unit that is directed to a specific speech goal, has a unique composition, contains unique stylistic features, and expresses a complete thought both in terms of content and form.

Will, as a linguistic genre, differs from other speech genres in that it has a specific speech purpose, composition, and style. In rhetorical studies, it was determined that the essence of the speech genre of will is to motivate a person to do something.

The research conducted on the will shows that there are several types of the will, such as a political will in the content of a petition, a religious will based on religious

advice and instructions, a will with legal force, and a will that is widely used among the public.

On the example of the booklet "Will" published in 2008 by "Yangi Asr Avlodi" publishing house in Tashkent, it can be said that according to its content, the religious will consists of advice and instructions addressed to the people of the Muslim world. This type of genre is in the form of hypertext in a religious style. Regardless of the fact that the religious testament consists of several macrottexts, its beginning begins with praising God. For example, "Praise be to God Almighty, who has made the human race superior to all others with knowledge!" May God's blessings, mercy and blessings be upon the Lord of the universe, mercy of the worlds, the excellence of the Prophets, Hazrat Muhammad Mustafa and his women and companions. Then it will be shown to whom the will is addressed. In this will, the bequest is addressed to children, grandchildren, and daughters-in-law. At the same time, the content of the will is expanded with the teachings, words, and narrations of the prophet. In the final part, show your beauty and give me the happiness of finding your approval. It ends with the meaning of supplication to Allah, such as "Grant us to stand among your beloved servants in your presence."

A legally binding will is a document stating the will of a person (the testator) to dispose of his/her property in case of his/her death. This type of will is written in an official style and consists of two microtexts. In the content of the first microtext, the place and time of writing of the will is indicated, and the name of the testator, residence address and the presence of tasks based on the will are reported. These parts are the introduction to the first microtext. In the main part, information about the bequeathed property, information about the recipient of the will, and the will of the testator are stated, and in the final part, the testator confirms this will with his signature. The content of the second microtext is the document confirming the written will, i.e. the writing, as well as the beginning of this part, the place and time of the writing of the will, as well as information about the person who notarized it,

the content of the main part is for circulation during the execution of notarial actions by the testator. and in the final part of the document, the state registry number and the information about the payment of a certain amount of state duty are given, and it is concluded with the signature of the notary. These wills are divided into types depending on the place of writing:

A will written in prison: a will executed in this order is mainly used for prisoners who are in prison and have to spend their last days in prison, and this will is made only in the presence of the prisoner, the head of the prison, and a lawyer.

In-flight will: this type of will is usually written by the captain of the aircraft or helicopter before the death in mid-air.

Wills written at sea, rivers and oceans: wills are written by a crew member or passenger who is about to die before reaching the shore, or verbally recorded by the ship's captain.

A will written officially in a notary's office or by calling the representatives of this organization at home: this will can be written at the end of life, it can be written by people who are on their deathbed, or in some cases, people can write a will while they are still conscious.

The will in conversational speech is expressed orally. For example, Bobomurod Hamdamov bequeathed "place my grave next to my teacher Komiljon Otaniyozov". It is observed that such types of wills are met in public, in front of the community, in the presence of friends, brothers, and relatives. In this case, the content of the will is intended to encourage the listeners to do something, and the form is in the form of a small, that is, a microtext, consisting of simple sentences.

When it comes to the style of the will, it is necessary to make the wills in the religious, formal, colloquial styles in a unique form in the religious, formal-business, colloquial style, from the lexicon specific to the religious, formal-business, colloquial style. it should be mentioned that it consists of a specific religious, formal-business, grammatical structure related to the style of speaking.

We have studied the testament written in the religious "Testament" booklet published as a warning to young people and the elderly, which was officially allowed to be published by the Office of Muslims of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and made a statistical analysis of it. You can see its result in this table:

Units representing "death" in the Uzbek language

Words, phrases used in the will Number of words used Indicator percentage

1 Death	7	24.1%
2 Paradise	2	6.8%
3 Hell	1	3.4%
4 Surrender	5	17.2%
5 Cave making	1	3.4%
6 Death	2	6.8%
7 Survive	1	3.4%
8 Close your eyes	1	3.4%
9 Corpse	1	3.4%
10 Moore	1	3.4%
11 Dead	3	10.3%
12 Doomsday	1	3.4%
13 Coffin	2	6.8%
14 Follow up to last trip	1	3.4%
Total:	29	100%

Analyzing the examples, we saw that the word death, which is mainly related to death, occupied the upper part of the concept of "death" in the religious will, and it came with several word combinations; If phrases such as "to die, after my death, on the days of my death, when I die" serve to clarify the main content of the will, "if the last words of those who are about to give up their lives before death are "La alaha illallah" , will definitely enter heaven." And in the speech, we can see the use of words that are taken from the testament, such as death, giving life, and heaven. In addition, the words and phrases related to the last acts of burial, which are included in the will, are "slowly closing the eyes, laying the body on the board, spreading the smell of musk in the barn so that the angels can enter, the last We can see such analyzes as accompanying on a trip, calling people to perform funeral prayers" in table.

The fact that people leave a will to their loved ones after their death is an event that attracts not only Uzbeks, but also the people of the whole world. In society and linguistics, testament is also considered as a separate direction, a type of genre. There are also specific types of bequests and inheritances. Even the religious and secular views written in the will differ depending on whether it is addressed to women or men. We explained it based on scientific statistical analysis.

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